

ForeFree - Putting the Tee in Vulnerability

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Introduction - In this paper, I will be going over an investigation of NFC (Near Field Communication) Cards at a Driving Range (A facility where golfers can practice their different golf swings) where I explored their operational intricacies, security considerations and data handling procedures.

This write-up aims to provide a comprehensive understanding for a diverse readership, by offering explanations that cover both conceptual and technical aspects.

There will be two parts to this paper. My initial investigation which started over a year ago, and then a follow-up visit, one year later.

Equipment - For this research project, I used the following Hardware / Software / Applications / NFC Cards:

- Proxmark3 Easy (512kb) running the Iceman Firmware
 - A hardware platform used for interacting with and investigating High and Low-frequency RFID credentials such as the ones used at this Driving Range.
- Android Phone with the MIFARE Classic Tool Application by IKARUS Projects
 - This is a low-level tool for reading, writing and analyzing MIFARE® Classic RFID tags. It provides several features to interact with (and only with) MIFARE® Classic RFID-Tags.
- Android Phone with the TagInfo Application by NXP Semiconductors
 - Provides detailed information about NFC tags and RFID cards, aiding developers and enthusiasts in understanding their capabilities and content.
- Gen1a Magic MIFARE Classic Cards
 - A special type of RFID Card that can be reprogrammed to mimic various types of MIFARE Classic Cards. These cards allow for easy cloning and modification of card data, including its UID (Unique Identifier).
- Driving Range issued NFC Card
 - A card that is issued to the consumer, that is used by the Ball Machine, in order to dispense balls that can then be used.

The Card in Question - The NFC Card used at the facility was powered by the MIFARE Classic 1K, a widely deployed High-Frequency chipset. These chips are prevalent across various industries due to being widely available and affordable.

A quick scan revealed its identity (UID) and type:

```
hf search
```


Figure 1: The above image is the display given after running "hf search" using the Proxmark3 Easy

```
Results:
- UID: 1E E6 5D 01
- ATQA: 00 04
- SAK: 08 [2]
- Card Type: MIFARE Classic 1K
```

The MIFARE Classic chipset, while widely used, possesses exploitable cryptographic vulnerabilities, which was the primary focus of my investigation.

There is a command 'hf mf autopwn' in the Proxmark that automates most of the MIFARE Classic card-only vulnerabilities, up to the extraction of all keys and data

```
hf mf autopwn
```

```
Result:
- Successful key recovery for each sector
```


Figure 2: The above image is the display given after running "hf mf autopwn" using the Proxmark3 Easy

Data Transfer and Replication - With the Proxmark3 Easy at my disposal and the successful **autopwn**, I had performed successful scans and data extraction from the NFC Driving Range Card.

The extracted data formed the foundation for the subsequent duplications of the card's information onto a blank Gen1a Magic MIFARE Classic Card, which is a special type of MIFARE Classic, used in duplication operations as it allows all of its data to be changed to reflect that of another MIFARE Classic including its Unique Identifier (UID). setting the stage for comprehensive testing.

Data Dump - The card's data was successfully extracted into a **.eml** file (A **.eml** file format is primarily used for email messages as it stores data in plain text.), which allows for specific line modifications. The initial data extraction presented as follows:

Block 0	1EE65D01A4080400032C48089DFCFB1D
Block 1	00000000000000000000000000000000
Block 2	00000000000000000000000000000000
Block 3	FFFFFFFFFFFFFFF078069FFFFFFFFFFFF
Block 4	303031302E3232343831202020202020
Block 5	303432302E3639343230202020202020
Block 6	32303233303931343138323133312020
Block 7	DDBCC221166FF078069DDBCC221166

(and so on...)

Table I: Hexadecimal data blocks

Double Trouble - To continue my investigation, I added \$20 worth of credit to my card and then dumped the credentials of the card into a **.eml** file. I then made a replica of my card using a Gen1a Magic MIFARE Classic Card

At the driving range, I took several swings, decreasing the available credit on the Original Driving Range Card, I applied the duplicated card to the reader, which showed I still had \$20 left. This was interesting, it means the credit on the card is stored locally, not utilizing any kind of back-end validation system to track balances.

While this is the intended purpose of MIFARE Classic Cards, there are still insecurities of having the credits stored locally in plain ASCII (Plain Text). When a system doesn't use any form of obfuscation, an individual like me can plainly see how the data is mapped. Since I know that the credits are untracked digitally, I am able to amend the balance to any amount that I'd like.

e.g.) Arcades tend to use this type of card solely as an identifier, which is then used to look up the user's information on a back-end system where the value is stored and retrieved as necessary.

Local Values - When analyzing the memory of the original credential with that of the duplicate, it revealed discrepancies in blocks 5 and 6 of the MIFARE Classics. These differences strongly suggested that any stored value resided in these blocks. To further analyze this vulnerability, I converted the hexadecimal contents of the blocks to ASCII

Original Card (Detail):

- Current credit according to the ball machine: \$10.22
 - Block 5: 303031302E32323438312020202020
 - Block 6: 32303233303931343138323133312020
- After Conversion
 - Block 5: 0010.22481
 - Block 6: 20230914182131

Duplicate Card (Detail):

- Current Credit According to ball machine: \$12.31
 - Block 5: 303031322E33313438312020202020
 - Block 6: 32303233303931343138313331312020
- After Conversion
 - Block 5: 0012.31481
 - Block 6: 20230914181311

Original Card

Duplicate Card

Block 5 Examination - Block 5 of the original card was where I had focused the majority of my attention.

The following hexadecimal data was examined in a hex editor:

- Block 5 [Raw]: 303031302E32323438312020202020
- Block 5 [ASCII]: 0010.22481

```

Offset(h) 00 01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 0A 0B 0C 0D 0E 0F Decoded text
00000000 30 30 31 30 2E 32 32 34 38 31 20 20 20 20 20 20 0010.22481
  
```

Figure 3: The above image is the the Hexadecimal value from Block 5, converted into ASCII

Discovering the “Source of Truth” - An alarming realization surfaced after analysing the data dump and converting the data to ASCII. I discovered the “source of truth”, for determining the card’s fund balance, resided solely within the card itself.

The ASCII interpretation of the hexadecimal data exposed the text “0010.22481.” This held vital information:

- 10.22: Representing the card balance, which indicates a remaining balance of \$10.22.
- 48: A numeric value corresponding to the tee height setting.
 - The significance of the ending “1” within this data element is presently under review and requires further investigation.

This revelation contrasted sharply with my initial hypothesis; that data was be centrally administered on a server or within the Driving Range’s equipment.

Editing and Testing the NFC Cards - I knew that the data was stored locally on the cards and where the information was in the data blocks.

Next, I decided to edit the card’s data for testing purposes; allowing me to determine the potential seriousness of the vulnerability.

In the following phase of the attempted exploitation, the objective was to modify the card’s data and write it onto a new card for the purpose of testing.

Editing Block 5 - Specifically, block 5 of the card’s data was modified to read as follows:

```
30 34 2 0 2E 36 39 4 2 0 20 20 20 20 20
```

Adjusting the above value via the hexadecimal editor resulted in the text “0420.69420”. This indicated the card should now operate as follows:

- 420.69: Representing the card balance, indicating a remaining balance of \$420.69
- 42: Representing the tee height setting.
 - The significance of the ending “0” within this data element is presently under review and requires further investigation.

Writing to the Cloned Card:

```
hf mf cload -f hf-mf-1EE65D01-dump.eml
```

I utilized the following command to write the edited data, including the updated block 5 changes, to the Cloned Card.


```
[usb] pm3 -->
[usb] pm3 --> hf mf cload -f hf-mf-1EE65D01-dump.eml
[+] loaded 1024 bytes from text file `hf-mf-1EE65D01-dump.eml`
[=] Copying to magic gen1a card
[=] .....[#] write block send data
error
[!] Can't set magic card block: 52
[usb] pm3 -->
[usb] pm3 --> █
```

Figure 4: The above image is the display given after running “hf mf cload...” using the Proxmark3 Easy

Verifying the cloned card:

```
hf search
```

```
Result:  
- UID: 1E E6 5D 01  
- ATQA: 00 04  
- SAK: 08 [2]
```

The reason why I did this was to verify that the UID of the cloned card, matched the UID of the original card.

```
[usb] pm3 --> hf search  
[\] Searching for ISO14443-A tag...  
[+] UID: 1E E6 5D 01  
[+] ATQA: 00 04  
[+] SAK: 08 [2]  
[+] Possible types:  
[+] MIFARE Classic 1K  
[-] proprietary non iso14443-4 card found, RATS not supported  
[+] Magic capabilities : Gen 1a  
[+] Prng detection: weak  
[#] Auth error  
[?] Hint: try `hf mf` commands  
  
[+] Valid ISO 14443-A tag found  
  
[usb] pm3 -->  
[usb] pm3 --> _
```

Figure 5: The above display, is what was used to verify that the UID of the Cloned Card, matches the UID of the Original Card

Testing the Cloned Card - With the newly cloned and edited card in hand, I went back to the Driving Range to test my hypothesis. I was greeted with the following when I slotted in the custom card.

- Currency Availability: The ASCII text '420.69' denotes the available currency balance on the card.
- Tee Height: The numeric value '42' denotes the tee height configuration.

Supporting Visual Evidence:

Figure 6: The above image is verification, that the updated card works as intended with the reader.

Secondary Testing (UID Whitelisting) - Now that I know that I am able to change the amount that is on the card, along with other minor settings, such as the tee height. I then wanted to test if the system had any type of security in place, to only allow “whitelisted” UIDs.

DNGO Hex Test - In order to test if UIDs were being Whitelisted, I decided to change the UID of a Duplicated Card that I knew worked originally. I changed the UID from:

Original UID ⇒ **DNGO UID**

```
Result:
- UID: 1E E6 5D 01
- ATQA: 00 04
- SAK: 08 [2]
```

```
Result:
- UID: 44 4E 47 4F
- ATQA: 00 04
- SAK: 08 [2]
```

*I chose **DNGO** as the UID, as a reference to myself (**TheDingo8MyBaby**).*

Figure 7: *The above image is verification, that the updated card works as intended with the reader.*

With testing concluded, it was clear to me that this site allows for any UID to work on their system, assuming that the other blocks of the card match up to their specifications.

This means that if I had malicious intent, I could, in theory, load a card with \$999.99 and use a UID that is unknown to the system, and drive for free.

What's also an issue is that if the UID is discovered and they decide to blacklist it, I can just create a new UID and continue to do the same thing indefinitely.

The Inevitable Return

ForeFree 2.0 - Teeing Up New Exploits

One Year Later - The goal for this continuation, is to disclose my new findings and new techniques used at the same location, one year later.

Why am I revisiting this? - In my original article, I discussed how it was possible to clone the data from the source card and write that data to a Gen1a Magic MIFARE Classic Card.

Since then, I have learned that not only can I edit and manipulate the data of my original card. I can do so, while at the Driving Range, with just my Android Smartphone.

Tagging Along - Looking back at **Figure: 2** (When I ran the original **autopwn**), I can reference the found key (DDBBCC221166) in the next steps.

By utilizing the **TagInfo** Android application, I am able to scan the Original Driving Range Card and see some basic information.

```
TagInfo
IC INFO  NDEF  EXTRA  FULL SCAN
Technologies Supported
ISO/IEC 14443-3 (Type A) compatible
Android Technology Information
Tag description:
  TAG: Tech [android.nfc.tech.Nfca,
  android.nfc.tech.MifareClassic,
  android.nfc.tech.NdefFormatable]
  Maximum transceive length: 253 bytes
  Default maximum transceive time-out: 618ms
Detailed Protocol Information
ID: 1C:61:22:32
ATQA: 0x0400
SAK: 0x08
Memory Content
Sector 0 (0x00)
[00] 1C 61 22 32 6D 08 04 00 | -a*2m...|
r-- 02 B9 00 FA B3 96 69 1D | .....i|
[01] 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 | .....|
rwl 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 | .....|
[02] 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 | .....|
rwl 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 | .....|
[03] FF:FF:FF:FF:FF:FF Factory default key
wxx FF:07:80 69
(r) FF:FF:FF:FF:FF:FF Factory default key
Sector 1 (0x01)
[04] -- -- -- -- --
??? -- -- -- -- --
[05] -- -- -- -- --
??? -- -- -- -- --
[06] -- -- -- -- --
??? -- -- -- -- --
[07] XX:XX:XX:XX:XX:XX (key unavailable)
??? -- -- -- -- --
    XX:XX:XX:XX:XX:XX (key unavailable)
```

Figure 8: Without the correct Key, I am only able to view the first few blocks of data.

Figure 9: Because I previously “pwned” this card, I am able to manually add the now known key to the TagInfo Dataset.

Figure 10: Now that the key has been entered into TagInfo, when I rescan the card, I am able to see the previously hidden data.

If I look back earlier in this paper (see I), I can verify that the data pulled from the Proxmark3, matches the type of data being displayed via TagInfo.

Mobile Manipulations - Now that I have the Key to Sector 1, and am able to view the stored data in Block 5. I can then utilize the MIFARE Classic Tool, Android application.

With MIFARE Classic Tool at my disposal, I can add a custom User Key similar to what we did with TagInfo.

Once the custom Key has been added, I will then specify within the application that I only want to scan and dump the data from Sector 1.

Figure 11: This is how the output is displayed, when dumping the data of Sector 1.

Now that I have the above data, I am able to adjust it to what I'd like it to be. What I primarily care about, is the data within the second row.

```
303038342E35363436312020202020
```

When I convert that Hex String to ASCII, it displays the following.

```
0084.56.461
```

As discussed previously, I know that this means my card currently has \$84.56 and that my Tee Height was last set to 46.

The only thing left to do now, is to change the data to whatever I'd like and save the configuration for future use.

For example, if I were to adjust the Hex String to the following.

```
303432302E36393436312020202020
```

That would then convert to

```
0420.69461
```

On-The-Fly Edits - All that's left to do now, is to actually write the data to the Original Driving Range Card.

Figure 12: I have adjusted the 2nd row of data, to write a balance of \$420.69.

Figure 13: Utilizing MIFARE Classic Tool, I am able to write data directly to the Original Driving Range Card. Additionally, I can save an edited dump file, and use that data source for future writes.

Figure 14: I am able to verify using TagInfo, that the data previously written to the card from the previous step, has successfully been written.

Exploiting Vulnerabilities for Personal Gain - If I were inclined towards unethical behavior, the vulnerabilities in NFC cards at the Driving Range could be exploited to create a black market service.

With tools like the MIFARE Classic Tool Application and TagInfo, I could position myself at the Driving Range, offering patrons unauthorized modifications such as selling card credits at a significantly discounted rate.

This exploitation could result in a substantial financial loss the Driving Range

Incorporating Additional Insights

MIFARE Classic Card Vulnerabilities: In the world of NFC card security, the MIFARE Classic 1K chipset is a recurring concern. Its inherent vulnerabilities make it susceptible to exploits, allowing attackers to recover sector keys and access data within the card.

Tools such as the Proxmark client make this process relatively straightforward. The use of **hf mf autopwn** is particularly noteworthy, as it can potentially, automatically recover keys for each sector.

Local Storage of Card Data: One of the notable revelations during my investigation was that the local storage of credit data, was on the card itself in ASCII.

Unlike systems that rely on centralized servers for balance validation, the MIFARE Classic card stores this information internally. While this approach aligns with its intended use, it introduces security risks, especially if the card is lost or stolen.

Conclusion

This investigation into NFC cards at The Driving Range has revealed critical vulnerabilities in the widely used MIFARE Classic 1K chipset. The study uncovered risks such as key recovery and the ease with which card data can be edited locally, highlighting significant security concerns associated with relying on outdated technologies. Tools like the MIFARE Classic Tool Application and TagInfo Application demonstrated how simple it is to manipulate and rewrite NFC card data using just a smartphone, including cloning, editing, and reprogramming card contents.

These findings emphasize the pressing need to adopt more secure practices in card-based systems. It is imperative to move beyond outdated technologies and implement more robust security measures to protect against potential exploits and ensure the integrity of card-based systems.

T H E D I N G O 8 M Y B A B Y

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